

Advancing a critical challenge in environmental remediation - a review of catalytically-driven production of aromatic amines from wasted nitroaromatic compounds

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Abstract: The present work reviews the continuous flow hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) to aromatic amines, highlighting its significance in sustainable chemical manufacturing. These processes offer enhanced efficiency, scalability, and safety compared to traditional batch methods, addressing the environmental concerns associated with NAC contamination. In this context, the flow mode processes of NACs hydrogenation may be considered as tools for catalytically-driven extraction of fine chemical products. Within this review, key aspects, including an overview of flow reactor designs—such as packed-bed and microreactors—optimizing heat and mass transfer are discussed. Additionally, various catalytic materials, including bimetallic nanoparticles and metal-organic frameworks, are explored for their improved stability and selectivity in NAC reduction. The kinetics of these reactions aids in understanding the factors affecting reaction, and mass transfer rates. Despite the advantages, challenges remain, including catalyst deactivation and reactor design complexities, particularly during scale-up for industrial applications. Future trends indicate a shift towards hybrid systems integrating photocatalysis and biocatalysis, enhancing the versatility of continuous flow processes. Ultimately, the adoption of these technologies is anticipated to play a crucial role in the circular economy by converting hazardous waste into valuable products, thereby fostering innovation and environmental preservation in the chemical industry.

1. Introduction

Nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) are simply chemical compounds with one or several $-\text{NO}_2$ groups attached to an aromatic ring. They are rarely found in nature and their occurrence is mainly attributed to human activities. This is due to their importance in manufacturing pesticides, explosives, different types of polymers, dyes, pharmaceuticals, and fine chemicals^[1].

This becomes a topic worth discussing because NACs are persistent contaminants and their accumulation not only poses a threat to the environment (soil and water), but their toxicity also threatens animals, including humans in that they

(NACs) are known to be carcinogenic, and mutagenic^[2]. This calls for the need for remediation of NACs in the most Circular Economy-based way, namely, catalytical reduction. The process in question enables the conversion of the $-\text{NO}_2$ groups into $-\text{NH}_2$ groups. The resulting product is an aromatic amine which can also be used in manufacturing pharmaceuticals, dyes, rubber chemicals, agrochemicals, and much more.^[2]

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This reduction can be done in batch or flow, continuous mode. The latter may not only provide greater efficiency, scalability, reaction control, and safety compared to batch processes but also may be considered as a tool for catalytically driven extraction of fine chemical products-aromatic amines [3]

2. Environmental Background

The $-\text{NO}_2$ in NACs reveals an electron-withdrawing nature that influences the electronic state of the aromatic ring. This makes NACs very important chemical intermediates in the manufacturing of a variety of large-scale, and specialized fine chemical products [4]. This can be attributed to the strong electronegativity of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group which is an electron-withdrawing group on an electron-poor aromatic ring. When the $-\text{NO}_2$ group is in *ortho* or *para* positions, the result is that the negative charge in the transition state becomes stabilized while when it is in *meta* position, the placement tends to be less effective [5]. Among a variety of NACs, nitrobenzene (NB) is industrially used as an intermediate for the production of rubber

chemicals, perfumes, dyes, and nitroaniline [6], 2,4,6-Trinitrotoluene (TNT) is a well-known explosive with high detonation velocity [7], 2,4-Dinitrotoluene (DNT) is an intermediate in the manufacturing of explosives and polyurethanes [8], nitronaphthalene (NN) is a very important intermediate in the syntheses of agrochemicals, pharmaceuticals, and dyes [9], while 2-Nitrotoluene (2-NT) is the basis of photographic chemicals, dyes, and other organic chemicals manufacturing [10]. Other commonly encountered NACs are presented in Figure 1.

These few examples are a small fragment of the overall importance of NACs, which due to their unique properties already became the largest group of chemicals used on an industrial scale [10]. Due to the wide application spectrum of NACs in a variety of industry branches they easily migrate to water directly or through leaching, to soil through adsorption or to air through *i.a.* emission of exhaust gases. Because NACs reveal persistent nature, they tend to accumulate overtime creating a serious threat to living things, especially humans [2, 4].

Figure 1. Common structures of NACs. Figure prepared with the use of data presented in the work cited under number [2]

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Most NACs can covalently bind to DNA, thus, they tend to be carcinogenic. The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) estimated that all NACs found in exhaust gases of diesel engines reveal genotoxicity^[11]. In turn, the American Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) indicated nitro-phenol compounds, and their potential mutagenic, carcinogenic, toxic, inhibitory, and endocrine-disrupting properties^[12]. Although inhalation of NACs-containing exhaust (diesel, gasoline) can be a cause of lung cancer they also pose a risk of damaging mechanisms of O₂ transfer in a human's body^[13]. Irrespectively, all these moieties no matter what their source is, find their way into ground- and wastewaters, as well as soil. This poses a serious threat, as NACs when consumed, pose a risk to the urinary track, pancreas, and nervous-system cancers

The toxicity of NACs ranges from chronic to acute as their level of concentration increases. This increase is not limited to soil, water, or air, it can also be observed in tissues of living organisms through bioaccumulation^[14]. As they accumulate in cellular structures, they can disturb the endocrine and reproductive activities in aquatic organisms while in humans they are usually linked to anemia, methemoglobinemia, and, as noted above, high cancer risks^[2, 15]. This accumulation does not only affect a single organism since the food chain enables the effect to be transferred from one organism to another. This threatens the animals with predatory behaviors including humans^[2, 16, 17].

In this context, although improved control over the use of explosive materials, pesticides, and disposal of industrial effluents can help in managing environmental threats caused by the occurrence of NACs, the actual alternative is to develop sustainable methodologies allowing reuse of these chemicals in a way that might fit into the circular economy^[18]. As such, the direct reduction of -NO₂ to -NH₂ groups is particularly important, because when considering wasted NACs as intermediates for the synthesis of aromatic amines creates strong incentives. Aromatic amines are the key building blocks for the manufacturing of photographic films, corrosion retarders, polymers, herbicides, dyes as well as drug formulations. The latter one is especially important, as aromatic amines are the key substrates to produce large-scale pharmaceuticals, including paracetamol, ibuprofen, acetaminophen (alternative to aspirin), bicalutamide, and

nilutamide (antiandrogens), linezolid (antibiotic for multidrug-resistant Gram-positive bacteria), and fosamprenavir, the anti-HIV drug, that found to be also effective in the treatment of COVID-19^[19-21].

For all these reasons there is a strong incentive to develop catalytical processes that could be aimed at effective reduction of NACs to aromatic amines. In such a scenario, appropriate materials and process designs could enable processes that could be recognized as a catalytically-driven extraction of aromatic amines from wastes containing NACs.

3. Reductions of Nitroaromatic Compounds

3.1. Batch Processes.

Traditionally, the NACs are reduced into their respective amines through chemical methods that can be applied both on laboratory and industrial scales. These resulting amines are relatively detoxified and useful in the synthesis of other chemicals such as dyes, pharmaceuticals, photographic chemicals, explosives, corrosion inhibitors, polymers, and rubber chemicals^[1, 22]. In this case, traditional methods are also identified as being carried out in batch mode. All reactants are loaded into a reactor and after a certain time, the products are offloaded. The process is repeated. This offers a certain level of effectiveness and control on reaction parameters due to the simplicity involved^[23]. The batch-mode reduction of NACs can be carried out in a few ways which are listed below.

Catalytic hydrogenation: a reactor is loaded with the NACs and a solvent, if necessary, the H₂ gas is pumped into the reactor, or a hydrogen-generating reagent is added, and a catalyst such as Ni, Pd, or Pt is introduced. Reaction conditions are set, it is usually high pressure and increased temperature, but it varies. The mixture is controllably agitated to provide homogeneity until the reduction is complete. This method offers good selectivity, high yields, and precise control over reaction conditions such as pressure and temperature^[24].

Metal/Hydronium (H₃O⁺) ion reduction: a reactor is loaded with the NACs to be reduced into a solvent such as water or an

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organic one, and a metal such as Sn, Fe, or Zn is introduced. The NACs get adsorbed on the metal surface. The metal acts as a source of electrons, and this is achieved by loading the reactor with hydrochloric acid or any other acid that acts as a source of hydronium. This assists in turning, for example, Fe into $\text{Fe}^{2+} + 2\text{e}^-$. The $2\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + 2\text{e}^-$ then becomes $\text{H}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This generated H_2 is very reactive hence turning $-\text{NO}_2$ adsorbed on metal surface into $-\text{NH}_2$. This reaction can be carried out at room temperature or slightly elevated temperatures with constant stirring to ensure homogeneity. This results in products that can easily be separated from the metal residues, and the control over temperature, pressure, acid addition, and overall yield is advantageous in this process [25].

Sulfide reductions: the NACs dissolved using water or organic solvents are loaded into a reactor, and the sulfide such as Na_2S or H_2S is added to serve as a reducing agent. The mixture is heated and continuously stirred for homogeneity while the temperature and pressure are also set according to the NACs type. This process is advantageous in that its simplicity from easy control of reaction parameters offers control over yield. However, it is a bit dangerous due to the flammability and toxicity of both Na_2S and H_2S . This calls for proper and cautious ventilation especially when H_2S is used [26].

Reductive alkylation (Leuckart Reaction): the NACs, formamide, or formic acid as a reducing agent, and any necessary solvents are loaded into a batch reactor, and then the temperature that usually requires reflux and pressure is set. The reduction of $-\text{NO}_2$ into $-\text{NH}_2$ is carried out while simultaneously the amine gets alkylated based on the present ketone or aldehyde. This intermediate formyl is hydrolyzed into amine too. This process offers necessary control over temperature and time to extract the needed products and prevent unnecessary side reactions [27].

These well-established methods are fairly advantageous when it comes to optimization of yield due to the possible and easy control over reaction parameters, but it becomes less impressive when the downtime needed for cleaning equipment in between batches and complicated handling of acids and reagents if the reduction is to be carried out for high quantities of

NACs under high pressures and temperatures which leads to safety concerns [28].

3.2. Flow-mode processes

Flow mode processes of NACs hydrogenation may offer significant advantages as compared to the batch ones. Apart from obvious ones, like continuous operation, high yields of NACs processing, reduced downtimes, improved automation, as well as control and safety [3, 29], the flow mode processes of NACs reduction have the potential to treat waste streams containing NACs as a source of aromatic amines. As such, these processes may serve as a tool for catalytically driven extraction of these fine chemical products from wastes of various origins. Unfortunately, most of the literature focuses on the batch reductions of NACs with an emphasis put on the development of novel catalytic materials [3, 29]. In this context, the authors find a gap in the literature. Hence, the present review puts a particular emphasis on flow-mode processes aimed at NACs remediation and simultaneous aromatic amines extraction.

In Figure 2, the batch (a) and continuous flow (b) reactors are simply represented as follows:

Figure 2. The batch (a) and continuous flow (b) reactors simplified representation. Figure reused from the work cited under number [3] under the CC BY license.

3.3. Reaction Mechanism

Mechanistic pathways of nitroaromatic reduction

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The process of reducing nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) is a multi-step process that generates different intermediates before fully converting the nitro group into an amine. It is the same in both batch and flow modes. Improving catalytic systems calls for enhancing effectiveness as well as the specificity of the reduction activity by understanding the sequential reduction steps and identifying important intermediate compounds. The reduction of NACs usually comes about gradually and can be separated into three primary stages: The first step involves converting the nitro group into a nitroso intermediate, followed by reducing it to a hydroxylamine intermediate, and finally reducing it into the corresponding amine. This complex procedure typically includes the movement of protons and electrons with the help of a catalyst [30–35].

First, the nitro group ($-\text{NO}_2$) is reduced by a single electron to produce a nitro radical anion. This anion then combines with another electron along with a proton to produce a nitroso compound ($-\text{NO}$). This first step of reduction is crucial and frequently sets the pace for the entire reaction. For example, when a catalyst like palladium on carbon (Pd/C) is present, the nitroaromatic molecule can attach to the catalyst surface area, promoting the effective transfer of electrons and enabling the creation of the nitroso intermediate [30–35].

The next step is to reduce the nitroso compound into hydroxylamine. This stage typically involves the introduction of both an electron and a proton. Stabilizing the intermediate as well as initiating the reaction can be achieved with the right catalyst. One instance is nickel-based catalysts such as Ni/SiO₂, which create a reactive surface that facilitates the conversion of nitroso compounds into hydroxylamines [30–35].

The hydroxylamine intermediate undergoes more reduction in the last step to create the targeted amine group ($-\text{NH}_2$). The catalyst's active sites usually suffice for this stage, which usually requires extra electrons and protons. This transformation can be catalyzed by iron-based catalysts like Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles by providing an appropriate environment for the transfer of hydrogen [30–35].

Intermediate and key products

Several important intermediates play a major role in influencing the reaction pathway and the final products during the reduction of nitroaromatics. These intermediates include nitroso compounds, hydroxylamines, and occasionally azo and azoxy compounds. Usually, the first step determines the rate because nitroso compounds which are characterized by the $-\text{NO}$ group are formed and quickly reduced to hydroxylamines. Despite being less unstable than nitroso compounds, hydroxylamines characterized by the $-\text{NHOH}$ group remain reactive and can be further reduced to produce the desired amine products. Reaction conditions and catalyst properties can have an impact on the stability of hydroxylamines and consequently the reduction's overall efficiency [30–35].

More intermediaries such as azo and azoxy compounds may form in less controlled conditions complicating the reduction pathway and signaling incomplete reduction or side reactions. By choosing the right catalyst or optimizing the reaction conditions, these byproducts can be minimized [30–35]. Agrochemicals, medicines, and dyes can all be made from aromatic amines like aniline which is eventually produced by the reduction process of nitrobenzene [36–38]. To create more effective and ecologically friendly catalytic systems for the reduction of nitroaromatic compounds, it is essential to comprehend these mechanistic pathways [30, 33, 34].

4. Flow mode reactors for the reductions of NACs

Different flow mode technologies can be applied in the continuous reduction of NACs. Five were described in this review, and their comparison is presented in [Table 4](#), after discussing in depth each one separately as follows.

4.1. Microreactors

Design and working principles.

Microreactors are miniature, continuous-flow reactors made up of capillary channels or microchannels within which chemical reactions take place. These reactors are usually built to handle small volumes of reactants, usually in the microliter to milliliter range, and are composed of materials like glass, silicon, or

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polymers^[39–41]. A microreactor's compact size offers several benefits such as better mass and heat transfer, accurate regulation of reaction parameters, and increased safety because of the reduced volume of hazardous substances^[39–41]. Reactants continuously flow through the microchannels in microreactors where they mix and react. This is the basic operational principle of microreactors^[41]. Since they have a high surface area-to-volume ratio, heat dissipation is efficient in preventing hot spots and improving temperature control.^[41] Furthermore, the laminar flow regime in microchannels reduces the production of byproducts and promotes uniform mixing. Microreactors are perfect for conducting fast or highly exothermic reactions because they allow for precise control over the reaction parameters^[39, 41].

To enhance the performance of microreactors, several features can be added. Catalytic reactions and their efficiencies can be significantly enhanced by coating the microreactors with Palladium or TiO₂. To increase the surface area for catalysis, porous ceramic, and zeolite materials can be used^[42]. For enhanced support and increased surface area, carbon nanofibers and organic polymer monoliths can be used^[43].

Microreactors have evolved from being single-step chemical reactors to sophisticated multiple steps reactors. They can nowadays be used to perform reagent injection, mixing, thermal management, and phase separation. They can be used in both the laboratories and industry^[41, 44–47]. Their scaleup is done not by increasing the size of a reactor but by operating multiple reactors parallelly. This maintains their benefits while increasing their production capacity in terms of quantity^[39, 42, 47]. They are often used when there is a need to deal with products of low-volume high-value, short shelf life, novelty, or those with dangerous manufacturing processes^[46, 48].

Microreactors provide several advantages over conventional batch reactors in the continuous flow reduction of nitroaromatics environment. Higher productivity and efficiency are achieved through the steady introduction of reactants and continuous removal of products made possible by the continuous flow setup. Microreactors improve mass transfer making sure that reactants and catalysts come into contact quickly which speeds up reactions and increases conversions^[39, 41, 46, 47].

Applications in selective hydrogenation of NACs.

Because of their superior control over reaction conditions, improved mass and heat transfer and shortened reaction times microreactors are very effective for reducing nitroaromatics in flow mode. These reactors are appropriate for both laboratory and industrial applications because they improve the synthesis of aromatic amines and related compounds with greater efficiency and selectivity^[39, 41, 46, 47]. Here are a few examples of their use:

Hydrogenation with Mesoporous Pd@SBA-15 Catalyst:

Microreactors fitted with a mesoporous Pd@SBA-15 catalyst have shown excellent efficiency in the continuous-flow hydrogenation of nitroaromatics to aromatic amines. The system converted 99% of the nitroaromatics in just 1 minute at a moderate temperature of 25°C and a flow rate of 1 mL/min demonstrating the reactor's capacity to support quick reaction kinetics and efficient catalyst use^[49].

Selective Hydrogenation to N-Arylhydroxylamines:

Utilizing a RANEY®-nickel catalyst treated with ammonia and DMSO microreactors is a highly efficient method for selectively hydrogenating nitroarenes to N-arylhydroxylamines. This process, which took advantage of the microreactor's improved mass transfer and precise control over reaction conditions produced a conversion rate of 99.4% and selectivity of 99.8% when carried out at room temperature and a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min^[50].

Pd/NHC Catalyzed Reduction and Coupling:

Microreactors utilizing a Pd/NHC (palladium-N-heterocyclic carbene) catalyst at 50 °C and a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min showed excellent yield and selectivity for the reduction and coupling of nitroaromatics to create diarylamines. The environment of the microreactor allows for effective mixing and quick heat transfer making it possible to synthesize complex molecules quickly and continuously^[51].

Improved safety, reaction efficiency, and selectivity are just a few of the many advantages that microreactors provide for the continuous-flow reduction and transformation of NACs. Because

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of their ability to precisely control reaction conditions, they are an excellent choice for a wide range of sensitive and complex chemical processes including safe exothermic reaction management, hydrogenation, and selective reductions [39–41, 49, 52].

4.2. Packed-Bed Reactors

Structure and functionality.

A packed bed reactor (PBR) is simply a reaction vessel where reactants flow over a catalyst found inside the reactor as a fixed or immobilized bed. They offer high conversion rates and continuity in operation at a low cost [53]. The simplified representation of a PBR can be seen in [Figure 3](#).

The reduction of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) such as 4-nitrophenol to their corresponding amines is one of the many catalytic processes carried out using packed-bed reactors (PBRs) [54].

To achieve effective and efficient reduction, PBR design and structure are essential [55]. The reactor vessel is the main part of a PBR and is usually a cylindrical column made of glass or stainless steel. Depending on its intended use, a vessel's dimensions can differ greatly between laboratory- and industrial-scales [56]. Reactor inlet and outlet ports allow reactants (like hydrogen gas and nitroaromatics) to be introduced, and products (like amines and unreacted hydrogen) to be removed [57]. The reactor additionally has temperature and pressure control systems to sustain the intended reaction conditions [58].

The packing material or catalyst particles are the central component of a PBR. This packing materials structure is made to retain desirable flow characteristics, increase mass transfer, and maximize surface area [59]. Metals like palladium (Pd) platinum (Pt) and nickel (Ni) are frequently used as catalyst particles. These particles are frequently supported by materials like alumina (Al_2O_3) silica (SiO_2) or activated carbon (C) [60–62]. Smaller particles offer more surface area but can result in higher pressure drops so the size and shape of these particles are

carefully selected to balance the pressure drop and surface area [63, 64].

Reactants must be evenly distributed throughout the packed bed to prevent channeling and guarantee effective catalyst use [64]. This is made possible by an outlet collection system at the bottom of the reactor to gather the product stream uniformly and an inlet distributor which can be a distributor plate or nozzle system at the top of the reactor [65]. A uniform residence time is ensured by minimizing back-mixing as reactants pass through the bed in the reactor's plug flow behavior which is the goal of its flow dynamics [66]. Controlling the pressure drop is essential to prevent excessive energy consumption and guarantee constant flow rates. The pressure drop is affected by various factors including particle size, shape, bed porosity, and flow rate [67, 68].

Another crucial factor is heat management because the reduction of NACs is an exothermic reaction [69]. Stable operation is guaranteed by effective heat management which also prevents hotspots [70]. Utilizing thermal insulation to preserve the appropriate temperature and stop heat loss as well as integrating heat exchangers such as jacketed reactors or external heat exchangers can help with this [70].

Since deactivation can happen because of fouling, poisoning, or sintering, catalyst regeneration and replacement are also essential [71]. PBRs frequently have designs that permit regular catalyst replacement as well as in-situ regeneration systems which involve running a regenerating agent through the reactor such as air or hydrogen [72]. A standard packed-bed reactor setup for example might contain a stainless-steel column that is one meter high and 0.1 meters in diameter. The column would be filled with 2–3 mm-sized palladium on carbon (Pd/C) catalyst particles. A perforated plate at the reactor's inlet would guarantee that hydrogen and nitrobenzene gas were distributed equally [73, 74]. The design would aim to achieve plug flow while minimizing back-mixing and upholding a laminar flow regime. A water jacket surrounding the reactor would help with heat management by keeping the temperature at 100°C [75, 76]. To periodically oxidatively regenerate the catalyst, the reactor would also have ports for introducing air [77].

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When the reactor is in operation, nitrobenzene and hydrogen are continuously fed into the top of it. As they pass through the packed bed and cross the Pd/C catalyst, nitrobenzene is reduced to aniline. The product stream would exit the reactor at the bottom carrying unreacted hydrogen and aniline and be routed to a separation system where aniline would be collected [38, 78].

To sum up, packed-bed reactors are essential for effectively reducing nitroaromatics to amines. For the best results, PBRs must have the right structure and design which includes the right catalyst distribution system, flow characteristics, and heat management. PBRs with sound design can be scaled up for industrial use, achieve high conversion rates, and make effective use of catalysts [73–75, 77, 78].

Figure 3. Simplified representation of a PBR. Figure reused from the work cited under number [74].

Applications of PBRs in NACs reduction.

Packed bed reactors are highly effective for the reduction of nitroaromatics in flow mode due to their ability to handle continuous processes with excellent control over reaction parameters [73, 74, 78]. The provided examples demonstrate the

versatility and efficiency of packed bed reactors in the reduction of nitroaromatics, making them valuable in both research and industrial applications.

High-Gravity Intensified Iron-Carbon Micro-Electrolysis for Dinitrotoluene Reduction

A study on the reduction of dinitrotoluene in a rotating packed bed (RPB) reactor with commercial iron-carbon (Fe-C) particles as packing material showed how successful this setup could be. The reduction efficiency was 68.4% in 100 minutes after optimizing variables like reaction time, liquid flow rate, and pH of the starting solution. By expanding the specific surface area and revitalizing the liquid-solid interface, the RPB reactor greatly accelerated reduction and prolonged the Fe-C particle's useful life [79].

Reduction of *p*-Nitrophenol Using a $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3@Au$ Composite Catalyst

High catalytic efficiency was demonstrated in a study on the reduction of *p*-nitrophenol in a packed bed reactor utilizing a $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3@Au$ composite catalyst synthesized using a green one-step method. A high rate of conversion from *p*-nitrophenol to *p*-aminophenol was caused by the gold which was dispersed at the atomic level. The catalyst was shown in the study to have good stability and recyclability which makes it a viable choice for industrial applications [80].

Selective Hydrogenation of Halogenated Nitroaromatics:

The selective hydrogenation of halogenated nitroaromatics to corresponding anilines has been accomplished with PBRs. A 99.8% yield of 3,4-dichloroaniline was obtained with minimal dehalogenation using a micropacked bed reactor, hydrogen gas, a reaction temperature of 40°C, and a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. This illustrates the reactor's capacity to sustain high selectivity in regulated settings [81].

Reduction of Nitroaromatics in a Micro-Packed Bed Reactor:

At 30°C, a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min demonstrated high conversion rates and selectivity for a variety of nitroaromatics [82].

Plug-flow reactor (PFRs):

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Plug-flow reactors (PFRs) can also be used for the continuous reduction of nitroaromatics even though they differ from packed bed reactors (PBRs) in that PBRs use a stationary catalyst bed while PFRs rely on the continuous flow of reactants with minimal axial mixing. With an emphasis on nitroaromatic concentrations commonly found in industrial wastewater, this two-step approach involved zero-valent iron reduction followed by the peroxidase-catalyzed capture of the resulting anilines. A total of 5 to 5.5 hours were needed for the enzymatic treatment which used soybean peroxidase in a PFR. A pH that was almost neutral and a hydrogen peroxide/substrate molar ratio of 1.5 were determined to be ideal. As evidence of the PFRs' efficiency in continuous reduction processes treated waters' apparent color was effectively reduced at Alum concentrations of 50 to 100 mg/L [83].

In conclusion, due to their reliable design and precise control over reaction parameters, PBRs provide a scalable and effective solution for the continuous reduction of nitroaromatics to amines. High conversion rates and catalyst longevity are guaranteed by the proper catalyst selection, optimized flow dynamics, and efficient heat management. PBRs' versatility in handling a range of nitroaromatic compounds from dinitrotoluene to 4-nitrophenol highlights their significance in both industrial and research settings. PBRs are indispensable in the field of catalytic reduction because as multiple applications have shown, they are not only highly effective in achieving targeted chemical reactions but also flexible enough to operate under a variety of conditions. [79–82].

4.3. Continuous Stirred-Tank Reactors (CSTR)

Operational principles.

In the chemical industry, continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTRs) are essential for the reduction of NACs to their corresponding amines. These reactors meet the needs of applications that require accurate control over reaction conditions and consistent product quality [84]. The core components of a CSTR consist of an agitation system (such as an impeller or mechanical stirrer) that guarantees full mixing of catalysts and reactants inside a cylindrical or spherical vessel usually made of

glass or stainless steel because of their strength and ability to withstand corrosion [85].

As illustrated in [Figure 4](#), the ports for inlet and outlet are placed carefully to enable the continuous input of reactants (such as hydrogen gas and nitroaromatics) and the output of products (amines and unreacted hydrogen) [85]. To avoid the development of concentration and temperature gradients, to ensure homogeneous reaction conditions, the agitation system becomes very crucial [84].

Control systems for pressure and temperature are essential parts of CSTRs as well to guarantee that the reaction environment is kept at optimal levels. The most common methods for controlling temperature are internal coils or external heating/cooling jackets which enable accurate reaction temperature control. Maintaining the appropriate pressure level for the reaction is made easier by valves and regulators. This is especially crucial in gas-phase hydrogenation reactions involving NACs [84, 85].

Securing a steady-state condition where the input and output flow rates are equal is the fundamental working principle of a CSTR. To maintain a constant volume inside the reactor, reactants are continuously added at a steady rate and products are continuously removed [86]. A constant reaction rate and product composition are produced by the constant stirring action which guarantees that the reactants are dispersed evenly throughout the reactor. To reduce NACs with high conversion rates and selectivity, this uniform mixing is necessary [85–87].

Industrial-scale operations can benefit from CSTRs because of their continuous operation mode which decreases downtime and boosts overall process efficiency [86, 87]. A CSTR can effectively control the exothermic nature of a reaction such as the reduction of nitrobenzene to aniline by avoiding hotspots that might deactivate catalysts or result in undesirable byproducts [88].

To maximize contact between the nitrobenzene and the catalyst surface, constant stirring makes sure that hydrogen gas is dispersed evenly throughout the liquid phase. High conversion rates and aniline selectivity are the outcomes of this [88–90].

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In terms of handling and regeneration of catalysts, CSTRs also provide flexibility. Because the catalyst is suspended in the reaction mixture, regeneration or replacement can be accomplished quickly and easily without requiring lengthy shutdowns. This is especially helpful in processes where fouling or poisoning of the catalyst could deactivate it [89]. The versatility of CSTRs in reducing NACs is further highlighted by their ability to operate at different scales ranging from laboratory to industrial [90].

For the reduction of NACs, CSTRs are highly effective due to their structure and operating principles. Uniform reaction conditions and superior product quality are guaranteed by the agitation systems through mixing in combination with precise temperature and pressure control. Because of its continuous flow operation which improves scalability and process efficiency, CSTRs are a reliable option for industrial applications where the reduction of NACs is necessary [91].

Use cases in reduction processes.

Continuous Stirred Tank Reactors (CSTRs) are effective for the reduction of nitroaromatics in flow mode because they can manage continuous processes and maintain uniform reaction conditions. The following instances show how effective and adaptable CSTRs are at reducing nitroaromatics which makes them useful for both laboratory and industrial uses [84–87].

Cherkasov et al. (2023) reviewed the use of CSTRs in the reduction of nitroaromatics as well as other applications in fine chemical synthesis. They highlighted that pseudo plug flow behavior which enhances residence time distribution and overall reaction control can be seen in CSTR cascades. Results showed that the system could save expenses by 70%, save energy consumption by 80%, and boost yield by up to 31%. These features make CSTRs very beneficial for continuous processes like nitroaromatic reductions that call for effective solids handling and mixing [92].

The same study also discussed the scalability possibilities of CSTRs in continuous-flow chemistry, especially in the production of pharmaceuticals. CSTRs are a reliable option for reducing nitroaromatics because of their ability to precisely control residence time and reactor conditions. The fact that

CSTRs process continuously means that they can handle hazardous materials safer than batch reactors [92, 93].

The selection of catalysts and the optimization of reaction parameters were emphasized as crucial elements for obtaining effective and selective results in another study on the continuous reduction of nitroaromatics. Inhibitors were frequently added to catalysts such as copper, nickel, cobalt, and palladium to prevent undesirable reactions. Efficient heat removal was essential to avoid thermal runaway, as the hydrogenation of nitro compounds is highly exothermic, releasing about 550 kJ/mol. CSTRs were used due to their capacity to control reaction conditions, thereby reducing catalyst poisoning and maintaining high conversion rates. Because of their continuous operation and ability to ensure uniform mixing, CSTRs were found to be suitable for industrial processes, including the production of aniline. It was also demonstrated that increasing reaction efficiency in these systems involved the use of solvents such as N-methylpyrrolidone and lower alcohols [94].

There are several benefits to using Continuous Stirred Tank Reactors (CSTRs) for reducing nitroaromatics and other chemical processes. In comparison to batch processing methods, they improve overall efficiency and yield while consuming significantly less energy and money, making them more sustainable for continuous manufacturing [92, 95, 96]. They ensure safe and efficient processing, especially in difficult reactions like nitroaromatic reduction, thanks to their capacity to handle solids and control extremely exothermic reactions [92]. CSTRs are ideal for handling hazardous chemicals in industrial applications due to their exceptional scalability and safety [92, 97]. By optimizing purity and lowering the requirement for intensive downstream processing, the precise control of residence time distribution (RTD) further improves product quality. CSTRs are now indispensable in pharmaceutical synthesis, fine chemical production, and continuous crystallization processes due to modern advances in design that combine several vessels into a single reactor system, improving reliability, scalability, and solid handling [92, 98].

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- ✓ Simple, robust cascade CSTR
- ✓ Ideal for multiphasic reactions
- ✓ Residence times up to 3 hours

In this work, the reviewed examples of the application of microreactors, PBRs, and CSTRs in continuous reduction of NACs can be summarized in [Table 1](#) presented below.

Figure 4. Multiphasic CSTR. Figure reused from the work cited under number ^[96] within the ACS AuthorChoice license.

Table 1. Examples of NAC reduction cases using microreactors, PBRs, and CSTRs

Reactor Type	Reactants	Reaction Conditions	Yield/Conversion	Key Findings	References
Microreactors	Nitroaromatics (e.g., nitrobenzene)	Pd@SBA-15 catalyst, 25°C, 1 mL/min flow rate	99.4% conversion, 99.8% selectivity	High efficiency in nitroaromatic hydrogenation at low temperatures.	^[49]
	Nitroarenes → N-Arylhydroxylamines	RANEY®-nickel, ammonia, DMSO, room temperature, 0.5 mL/min	High yield and selectivity	Precise control over reaction conditions enabled high selectivity and conversion rates.	^[50]
	Nitroaromatics → Diarylamines	Pd/NHC catalyst, 50°C, 0.8 mL/min	68.4% degradation in 100 minutes	Efficient reduction and coupling of nitroaromatics, ideal for continuous flow processes.	^[51]
PBRs	Dinitrotoluene → Amines	Fe-C particles, rotating packed bed, high-gravity, optimized pH	68.4% degradation in 100 minutes	Accelerated degradation through high-gravity and liquid-solid interface improvements.	^[79]
	p-Nitrophenol → p-Aminophenol	Fe(OH) ₃ /Fe ₂ O ₃ @Au catalyst, green synthesis	High conversion	Atomic-level dispersion of gold provides high catalytic efficiency and recyclability.	^[80]
	Halogenated nitroaromatics → Anilines	Micropacked bed, hydrogen, 40°C, 0.5 mL/min	99.8% yield	High selectivity for aniline production with minimal dehalogenation.	^[81]

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CSTRs	Nitroaromatics → Hazardous intermediates	CSTR cascades for hazardous intermediate production, optimized RTD	Up to 31% yield increase, 80% energy savings	Optimized for hazardous intermediate production (e.g., diazomethane) with significant energy and cost savings.	[92]
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4.4. Membrane reactors.

Membrane reactors greatly increase the efficiency and selectivity of chemical transformations by combining the reaction and separation processes into a single apparatus [99–101]. A reaction chamber integrated with a selective membrane which allows certain reactants or products to pass through while retaining others is the typical construction of these devices [99–103]. Because it permits the continuous removal of hydrogen or other gaseous reactants, this configuration is especially beneficial for the reduction of NACs to their corresponding amines [100, 101, 104]. The simplified representation of a membrane reactor used in the continuous reduction of NACs is presented in [Figure 5](#) and [Figure 6](#).

The membrane itself, which can be made of ceramic, polymers, or metal composites, is an essential structural element of membrane reactors [99, 105]. Because of the selective permeability of these membranes, hydrogen can permeate through them while the larger nitroaromatic molecules are kept inside the reaction chamber [106, 107]. To sustain high reaction rates and stop reactant dilution this selective permeability is necessary [99, 101, 107]. The actual reaction chamber has ports for the continuous addition of reactants and the extraction of products and is frequently built from sturdy materials like glass or stainless steel [101, 108–110].

Because they can combine the processes of separation and reaction, membrane reactors improve selectivity and efficiency and are therefore very effective for the reduction of nitroaromatics in flow mode [99–101]. The following are a few examples of their use, and they are summed up in [Table 2](#).

The catalytic membrane with gold nanoparticles, PAN-PDAu membrane demonstrated remarkable catalytic activity for reducing nitroaromatic compounds specifically 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) under continuous flow conditions. The membrane was

produced by employing catechol groups to reduce and anchor gold nanoparticles. Under optimal conditions of pH 9.6 and 1 bar of pressure, it effectively converted 4-NP to 4-aminophenol (4-AP), though at higher pressures the effectiveness decreased. The membrane exhibited remarkable stability, reusability, low leaching of gold nanoparticles, and noteworthy antibacterial characteristics indicating its potential for environmental remediation and diverse catalytic uses [111].

The study by Dotzauer et al. (2009) employed layer-by-layer (LBL) deposition of polyelectrolyte and metal nanoparticle films on porous alumina, polycarbonate, and nylon membranes to enhance catalytic activity as shown in [Figure 5](#). These membranes were used to immobilize gold nanoparticles that were made by citrate reduction. Reduction reactions were carried out using 100 mM NaBH₄ and 1 mM nitro compound along with membrane modifications such as PAA/PAH/Au nanoparticle films. Rate constants varied from 0.015 to 0.018 cm/s across different membranes and membrane gold loading varied (alumina: 0.9 mg polycarbonate: 0.16 mg nylon: 1.8 mg). With the help of solution flux adjustments, the membranes showed high catalytic activity, selectively, reducing nitro groups and regulating product distribution. Elevated temperatures led to a rise in the ratio of amino to nitroso products suggesting that the reaction effectively converted nitroso compounds into amines [112].

Figure 5. Typical reduction of NACs using a membrane reactor. Figure reused from the work cited under number [112] with the permission of ACS Publications.

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In another study by Liu et al. (2020), a novel stacked catalytic membrane microreactor with multilayered microchannels and gas-permeable poly(dimethylsiloxane) membranes with immobilized catalysts was created for gas-liquid-solid reactions. Along with addressing flow maldistribution and throughput issues, the design maximizes gas utilization. The reactor demonstrated effective and stable operation for 50 hours when tested using nitrobenzene hydrogenation over palladium nanocatalysts. Adding layers improved durability and provided a scalable solution for catalytic reactions involving multiple phases [113].

In catalytic processes, membrane technology and microreactors can be combined to provide synergistic advantages. Membrane reactors, including those with palladium or platinum membranes, perform better than conventional systems in the hydrogenation of nitrobenzene to aniline. At 120°C and 0.5 MPa H₂, a platinum microchannel sintered membrane reactor produced a yield of 19.28 mol_{aniline} h⁻¹ L⁻¹, much higher than the 1.01 mol_{aniline} h⁻¹ L⁻¹ from trickle-bed reactors. This design is highly suitable for industrial use because it improves mass transfer, efficiency, and stability while retaining high selectivity and adaptability to various nitroaromatic substrates [114].

To sum up, the reduction of nitroaromatic compounds has advanced significantly with the use of membrane reactors. Their

special design offers significant advantages in terms of efficiency selectivity and continuous operation by fusing reaction and separation into a single unit [99, 101, 108]. Research has consistently shown that membrane reactors are efficient for a range of processes including the synthesis of pharmaceutical intermediates and the hydrogenation of nitrobenzene [111, 114]. Membrane reactors are essential in industrial processes that need to reduce NACs efficiently because of their capacity to sustain ideal reaction conditions and enable continuous operation. Membrane reactors are the preferred method for complex chemical syntheses because of their high selectivity and yield which are made possible by the continuous separation made possible by the membrane [99, 108, 111, 112, 114].

Figure 6. An active metal sintered membrane reactor for NACs reduction. Figure reused from the work cited under number [102] with the permission of the Royal Society of Chemistry.

Table 2. Summary of case examples of NAC reduction using membrane reactors

Membrane Type	Reactants	Reaction Conditions	Yield/Conversion	Key Findings	References
Gold nanoparticle catalytic membrane (PAN-PDAu)	4-Nitrophenol (4-NP) → 4-Aminophenol (4-AP)	pH 9.6, 1 bar pressure	High conversion at optimal conditions	Stable, reusable, low gold nanoparticle leaching, antibacterial properties for environmental remediation.	[111]

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LBL deposition on alumina, polycarbonate, nylon	Various nitro compounds	100 mM NaBH ₄ , 1 mM nitro compound, temperature-sensitive	Rate constants: 0.015 - 0.018 cm/s	High catalytic activity with product distribution controlled by solution flux and temperature.	[112]
multilayered microreactor with gas-permeable poly(dimethylsiloxane) membrane	Nitrobenzene → Aniline	Palladium catalyst, 50 hours of operation	Effective for 50 hours	Scalable design for gas-liquid-solid reactions with improved durability and gas utilization	[113]
platinum microchannel sintered membrane	Nitrobenzene → Aniline	120°C, 0.5 MPa H ₂	19.28 mol AN h ⁻¹ L ⁻¹	Significantly higher yield than conventional systems, with improved mass transfer and stability	[114]

4.5. Photocatalytic flow reactors.

In the process of photocatalysis, a material known as a photocatalyst (Si, TiO₂, ZnO, WO₃, CdS, ZnS, SrTiO₃, SnO₂, WSe₂, Fe₂O₃) absorbs light energy, usually from the visible or ultraviolet (UV) spectrum, and uses it to catalyze chemical reactions^[115–117]. Reactants that would normally be slow or unreactive can now be activated through this light-driven process. By maintaining steady illumination and improving reactant mass transfer over immobilized photocatalysts, photocatalysis provides an extremely effective and scalable approach for carrying out reduction reactions, such as the conversion of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) to amines, in continuous flow mode^[37, 115–117].

Due to their ability to use light energy to catalyze reactions, photocatalytic flow reactors have become a promising technology for the reduction of NACs^[37, 115–118]. These reactors usually have a reaction chamber in which light, usually from UV lamps or LEDs, is directed at the photocatalyst to initiate the catalytic process. To maximize contact between the reactants

and the photocatalyst, the design guarantees ideal light distribution and flow dynamics^[37, 115–119].

The photocatalyst, which is typically immobilized on a support material to ensure stability and prevent loss during the reaction is the central component of a photocatalytic flow reactor. Some common photocatalysts such as zinc oxide (ZnO), titanium dioxide (TiO₂), and various doped semiconductors are known for their high photocatalytic activity under UV or visible light. To provide the photocatalyst with enough illumination, the reaction chamber is usually made of materials that permit light penetration such as quartz or transparent polymers^[37, 115–119]. Photocatalytic flow reactors are highly effective for the reduction of nitroaromatics in flow mode due to their ability to harness light energy to drive chemical reactions^[37, 115–119].

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Figure 7. Illustration of the main events in semiconductor photocatalysis. Figure reused from the work cited under number [115] under the CC-BY license

According to [Figure 7](#), semiconductor photocatalysis involves several key steps: 1. A photon excites an electron from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB), forming an exciton. 2. The exciton then separates into free charge carriers (an electron and a hole), which migrate to the surface. 3. The electron becomes trapped in the material. 4. The hole also becomes trapped. 5. They may recombine, emitting light or dissipating energy. 6. Substrate molecules adsorb to the surface, where they are oxidized by the electron and reduced by the hole. 7. Finally, the modified substrates detach from the surface and enter the solution for further reactions [115].

Here are several examples that highlight the versatility and efficiency of photocatalytic flow reactors in the reduction of nitroaromatics, making them valuable tools in both academic and industrial settings. They were also summarized in [Table 3](#).

In the work of Navarra et al. (2023), the photocatalytic reaction was carried out using commercial TiO₂ (P25) and a photocatalytic aerogel, which consisted of P25 embedded in syndiotactic polystyrene (sPS) aerogel (sPS/P25 aerogel), as the photocatalysts to investigate the photocatalytic reduction of nitrobenzene (NB) to aniline (AN). The process included utilizing various alcohols as hydrogen sources with ethanol turning out to be the most efficient. Under optimal conditions (0.5 g/L photocatalyst dosage, 50% ethanol, and UV irradiation for 180 minutes), the procedure produced an astounding AN yield of more than 99%. Both P25 and sPS/P25 aerogel demonstrated high efficiency, with NB conversion rates of 99% and 95%, respectively. Its remarkable yield and the simplicity with which sPS/P25 aerogel can be extracted from the solution demonstrate

the technology's potential for industrial scale-up, providing an efficient and environmentally friendly way to produce aniline (AN) without the use of hazardous metals or high-pressure hydrogen. This suggests that sPS/P25 aerogel is a practical choice for industrial use [37].

The work by Tang et al. (2024) presented a new heteropolytungstate catalyst that combines {TeW₉O₃₃} and [Ru(C₆H₆)Cl₂]₂: Cs₄Na₂H₂[Te₂W₂₀O₇₂(H₂O)]{(C₆H₆)Ru₄}·12H₂O. With a 99.8% yield in the reduction of nitrobenzene to aniline, this compound demonstrated remarkable photocatalytic activity. Using visible light for the reduction process effectively demonstrated high stability and reusability in cyclic tests. With N₂H₄·H₂O as the reductant, the catalyst demonstrated a high turnover number (TON = 330) and turnover frequency (TOF = 24 h⁻¹) indicating its potential for both economical and environmentally friendly aniline production [36].

Utilizing oxygenated aqueous suspensions of TiO₂, this study examined the photocatalytic degradation of 2-, 3-, and 4-nitrophenol, where hydroxyl radicals were essential in starting the degradation process. The formation of dihydroxynitrobenzenes and subsequent mineralization into nitrate and ammonium ions was caused by these radicals attacking the aromatic rings. Complete mineralization was confirmed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Two phases of the degradation process included the rapid opening of aromatic rings and the later, slower oxidation of aliphatic compounds. The principal oxidants were hydroxyl radicals, which targeted the ortho and para positions of the nitrophenols preferentially. Meanwhile, the nitro group promoted electrophilic substitution. Since the pH of the solution greatly affects the reduction of the nitro group to an amine, the presence of ammonium ions suggested the existence of active reductive pathways. Overall, the photocatalytic method demonstrated significant mineralization, indicating the potential for effective environmental remediation and emphasizing the role of both oxidative and reductive pathways [118].

All things considered; photocatalytic flow reactors are a major development in the reduction of nitroaromatic compounds. They are designed to operate continuously and efficiently with an illuminated reaction chamber and an immobilized photocatalyst.

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Numerous applications including the treatment of nitroaromatic pollutants in wastewater and the reduction of nitrobenzene have been shown in studies to be effective with them. Photocatalytic flow reactors are essential for industrial and environmental

processes that need to reduce NACs efficiently because of their capacity to maintain ideal reaction conditions and enable continuous flow [36, 37, 115–119]

Table 3. Summary of some use cases of photocatalysts

Photocatalyst	Reactants	Reaction Conditions	Yield/Conversion	Key Findings	Reference
TiO ₂ (P25) and sPS/P25 aerogel	Nitrobenzene (NB) → Aniline (AN)	0.5 g/L catalyst, 50% ethanol, UV irradiation (180 min)	99% (P25), 95% (sPS/P25 aerogel)	High NB conversion rates, potential for industrial scale-up using sPS/P25 aerogel.	[37]
Heteropolytungstate ((TeW ₉ O ₃₃), [Ru(C ₆ H ₆)C ₁₂] ₂)	Nitrobenzene (NB) → Aniline (AN)	Visible light, N ₂ H ₄ ·H ₂ O as reductant	99.8% yield, TON = 330, TOF = 24 h ⁻¹	High stability, reusability, and environmentally friendly aniline production.	[36]
TiO ₂ (aqueous suspensions)	2-, 3-, 4-nitrophenol	Oxygenated aqueous suspensions, hydroxyl radicals as key oxidants	Complete mineralization confirmed by HPLC	Hydroxyl radicals initiate degradation, and mineralization to nitrate and ammonium ions.	[118]

Table 4. Summarized comparison of described reactors used in NACs reduction

Reactor Type	Design Features	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
Microreactors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Capillary/microchannels. · High surface area-to-volume ratio. · Precise control of reaction parameters. · Use catalysts such as Palladium and TiO₂. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhanced mass and heat transfer. · High selectivity. · Suitable for fast/exothermic reactions. · Scalable through parallel operation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Limited to small volumes. · Challenging scale-up for large production. 	[39–41, 44–48, 120–126]

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Packed-Bed Reactors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Stationary catalyst bed. · The continuous flow of reactants over a catalyst (Pd, Pt, Ni catalysts). · Cylindrical reactor design with stainless steel/glass vessels. · Temperature and pressure control systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · High conversion rates. · Effective heat management. · Long catalyst life with in-situ regeneration systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Risk of pressure drop due to small particle size. · Flow distribution challenges. 	[53, 55, 56, 59, 64–67, 73, 74, 127, 128]
Continuous Stirred-Tank Reactors (CSTR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Stirred vessel for uniform mixing. · Continuous input of reactants and output of products. · Agitation system (impeller or mechanical stirrer). · External heating/cooling jackets for precise temperature control. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Homogeneous reaction conditions. · High efficiency for handling solids and exothermic reactions. · Continuous operation reduces downtime. · Scalable for industrial applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · High energy consumption for mixing. · Not ideal for reactions requiring limited mixing. 	[29, 44, 49, 84, 85, 92, 95–98, 121, 129, 130]
Membrane Reactors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reaction chamber integrated with selective membrane. · Continuous removal of reactants/products. · Use of ceramic, polymer, or metal membranes. · Ports for continuous addition and extraction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Simultaneous reaction and separation. · High selectivity and efficiency. · Effective gas-liquid reactions. · Reduced reactant dilution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Membrane fouling issues. · High initial setup cost. · Potential deactivation over time. 	[72, 98, 101, 105, 107, 108, 113, 131, 132]
Photocatalytic Flow Reactors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reaction chamber illuminated with UV/visible light. · Immobilized photocatalyst on support materials (TiO₂, ZnO, WO₃, etc.). · Transparent materials for light penetration (quartz, transparent polymers). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · High photocatalytic efficiency. · Low energy consumption using visible light. · Suitable for environmentally friendly processes. · Scalable for continuous operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Limited by light penetration. · Deactivation of photocatalyst over time. · Potential issues with long-term stability. 	[36, 88, 115–119, 133–136]

5. Catalysts Used in Flow Mode Processes

By offering a quicker, more kinetically favorable pathway without changing thermodynamics or being consumed, a catalyst speeds up a chemical reaction and allows for multiple cycles of use.

The reduction of nitroaromatics to amines is an essential transformation in organic synthesis, particularly in the production

of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and dyes. Catalysts play a crucial role in this process, with various types of homogeneous, heterogeneous, nanocatalysts, and polymer-supported catalysts being employed depending on the specific requirements and desired outcomes [2, 4, 137]. These are summed up in [Table 5](#).

Homogeneous catalysts

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In homogeneous catalysis, reactants involved in the reaction and the catalyst exist in the same phase. Homogeneous catalysts are highly valued for their reusability, high selectivity, and efficiency in reducing nitroaromatic NACs [138–141]. They also frequently function well in mild environments and offer both environmental and economic advantages. However, there are several obstacles to overcome such as challenges with catalyst recovery and separation, sensitivity to reaction conditions, risks to the environment and human health from heavy metals, and expensive costs especially when dealing with precious metals [138–142].

Overall, selectivity, reaction conditions, and process efficiency are greatly impacted by the catalyst and mechanism choices. Developing new catalysts and improving upon existing ones is the goal of ongoing research aimed at improving the sustainability and suitability of these catalytic systems for environmental remediation and industrial synthesis [139–141, 143].

Homogeneous catalysts such as Palladium (Pd), Nickel (Ni), Ruthenium (Ru), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Copper (Cu), Gold (Au), Platinum (Pt), and Rhenium (Re) complexes are commonly used in flow mode processes. These catalysts provide a consistent and effective reduction of nitroaromatics because they dissolve in the reaction medium [138–140, 143–146]. The way they work is that they create metal-hydride species which help the nitro groups absorb hydrogen. For example, whereas Ni complexes selectively generate primary amines, Pd complexes usually involve processes like oxidative addition and reductive elimination [146]. These catalysts are preferred because of their excellent selectivity, tolerance to mild reaction conditions, and adaptability to continuous flow systems. But some issues like catalyst recovery, cost, and environmental impact must be resolved particularly when dealing with precious metals [138–140, 143–146].

Heterogeneous Catalysts

Heterogeneous catalysts exist in different phases from both the reactants and products. The reduction of NACs which are important pollutants in environmental and industrial settings is a crucial function of heterogeneous catalysts. Catalysts like these

can be separated easily from reaction mixtures, reused, and are stable in reaction conditions, among other benefits. Several research studies have investigated the mechanisms as well as the efficacy of diverse heterogeneous catalysts, emphasizing their advantages as well as drawbacks [147–149].

Heterogeneous catalysts, like Palladium on Carbon (Pd/C), Nickel-based catalysts (e.g., Raney Nickel), Ruthenium on Carbon (Ru/C), and Iron-Nitrogen-Carbon (Fe-N-C) catalysts, offer advantages in flow mode reduction of NACs due to their ability to be easily separated from the reaction mixture, reused, and maintained under different reaction conditions. Adsorption of the nitroaromatic compound and hydrogen on the catalyst surface is typically the first step in the reduction mechanism after which hydrogen is transferred to the nitro group [150–153]. Because of their stability, high activity, and suitability for continuous processes, these catalysts are especially helpful in industrial settings. They may however be vulnerable to problems like complex preparation, deactivation, and sintering [147–153].

Polymer-Supported Catalysts and Nanocatalysts

In the field of catalysis, nanocatalysts, and polymer-supported catalysts represent innovative materials for the reduction of NACs. By utilizing the distinct characteristics of polymers and nanomaterials, these catalysts improve catalytic activity, selectivity, and stability while providing innovative solutions for industrial and environmental remediation [154–160].

Catalysts that function at the nanoscale, usually in the range of 1 to 100 nanometers are called nanocatalysts. Their high surface area to volume ratio boosts their catalytic activity. They also have other special properties. Nanocatalysts have exceptional catalytic properties because of their high surface area-to-volume ratio and quantum size effects [161–164].

Catalysts supported by polymers combine the catalytic qualities of active metal sites with the flexibility and tunability of polymers [154–157].

Nanocatalysts, including nanoparticles of Platinum (Pt), Palladium (Pd), Nickel (Ni), Ruthenium (Ru), Gold (Au), Copper

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(Cu), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), and Silver (Ag), are distinguished by their high surface area-to-volume ratio and unique electronic properties, enhancing their catalytic activity [132, 154–165].

For example, platinum nanoparticles aid in the adsorption and transfer of hydrogen whereas bimetallic nanoparticles (e. g., Pd-Au) combine the advantages of two metals to create a complementary combination [166]. Due to their larger surface area, nanocatalysts are excellent for a variety of catalytic processes including continuous flow systems, and are particularly effective at reducing nitroaromatics. However, they may run into difficulties with stability, aggregation, leaching, and high costs [161–164].

Moreover, porous materials like metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are often employed to confine noble metals

in the reactor, which enhances the catalyst's activity by preventing nanoparticle aggregation. This confinement effect not only boosts the catalytic reduction of nitroaromatics but also improves recyclability and operational stability [167].

In general, the reduction of nitroaromatics is greatly impacted by catalyst selection in terms of selectivity, reaction conditions, and process efficiency. To improve sustainability and suitability for industrial and environmental processes, ongoing research is concentrated on creating new catalysts and refining those already in use. The selection of catalysts depends on various factors such as reaction requirements, cost considerations, and environmental impact since each type of catalyst possesses distinct advantages and challenges [159, 161–164].

Table 5. Catalysts used in flow-mode reductions of aromatic nitro compounds.

Category	Subcategory	Catalysts	Mechanism	References
Homogeneous Catalysts	Transition Metal Complexes	Palladium (Pd), Nickel (Ni), Ruthenium (Ru), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Copper (Cu), Gold (Au), Platinum (Pt), Rhenium (Re), Silver (Ag), Molybdenum (Mo), Iridium (Ir)	Formation of metal-nitro complex, followed by hydrogen transfer.	[138–146, 168, 169]
Heterogeneous Catalysts	Metal on Carbon or Oxide Supports	Palladium (Pd) on Carbon, Nickel (Ni) Catalysts, Ruthenium (Ru) on Carbon, Iron (Fe) Catalysts, Cobalt (Co) Catalysts, Copper (Cu) Catalysts, Gold (Au) Catalysts, Platinum (Pt) on Carbon, Rhenium (Re) Catalysts, Silver (Ag) Catalysts, Molybdenum (Mo) Catalysts	Adsorption of hydrogen and nitro compound on the metal surface, followed by hydrogen transfer.	[91, 115, 118, 147–149, 153, 166, 169–173]
Nanocatalysts	Metal Nanoparticles	Platinum (Pt), Palladium (Pd), Nickel (Ni), Ruthenium (Ru), Gold (Au), Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Silver (Ag), Rhenium (Re), Bimetallic Nanoparticles (e.g., Pd-Au, Pt-Ru), Rhodium (Rh), Iridium (Ir)	Facilitate adsorption of hydrogen and nitro compounds, enabling hydrogen transfer.	[17, 27, 111, 112, 131, 132, 154–156, 158–166, 174, 175]
Polymer-Supported Catalysts	Metal on Polymer Supports	Palladium (Pd), Nickel (Ni), Ruthenium (Ru), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Copper (Cu), Gold (Au), Platinum (Pt), Rhenium (Re), Silver (Ag), Iridium (Ir)	Adsorption of nitro compound on polymer-supported metal, followed by hydrogen transfer.	[154–166]

6. Kinetics of NACs Reduction in Flow Mode Systems

Studies of the kinetics of NAC reduction in continuous flow mode offer important information about the efficiency and reaction rates of catalytic systems operating in steady-state conditions. Using

reliable techniques to analyze reaction rates and comprehending the variables influencing the kinetics of these reactions in a continuous flow setup is crucial for optimizing these systems [176–179].

Methods for Analyzing Reaction Rates.

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Several methods are used to analyze reaction rates in continuous flow systems allowing for accurate tracking of reactant and product concentrations over time. Using online spectroscopic methods like UV-Vis spectroscopy is one popular approach that enables real-time reaction progress monitoring [160, 175–181]. For instance, the appearance of the peak corresponding to 4-aminophenol and the decrease of the characteristic absorbance peak of 4-nitrophenol can be used to track the reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol [160, 176, 178, 179].

An additional effective method for kinetic studies is high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). HPLC can be used to analyze the reaction mixture at various time intervals to give a comprehensive overview of the concentrations of starting materials, intermediates, and final products thus allowing the creation of detailed kinetic profiles. This method is especially useful in reactions with multiple intermediates that are highly complex [177–180].

The reaction kinetics concerning volatile compounds can be studied using gas chromatography (GC) as well as mass spectrometry (GC-MS) methods. Identifying and measuring the components involved in a reaction helps to gain an understanding of the reaction's mechanism and speed [131, 179, 182–184].

Computational approaches like kinetic modeling and simulation are essential for comprehending and forecasting reaction behavior in addition to these analytical strategies. Researchers can derive rate constants and clarify the reaction mechanism by fitting experimental data into kinetic models. This process facilitates catalyst design and reaction condition optimization [179, 185–188].

Factors Affecting Kinetics in Continuous Flow

The catalyst properties, reactor design, temperature, pressure, and flow rates are some of the factors that affect the kinetics of NAC reduction in continuous flow systems.

Reactor Design: How the flow reactor is designed, whether it be a packed-bed reactor, microreactor, or tubular reactor, has a

substantial impact on the speed of the reaction. The selection of the reactor affects the distribution of residence time, the effectiveness of mixing, and the transfer of heat, all of which are important for maintaining consistent reaction conditions and attaining high conversion rates [189–191].

Flow Rates: Reactant and solvent flow rates affect the amount of reaction and product yield by determining how long the reactants stay in the reactor. Ideal flow rates prevent problems like channeling and insufficient mixing while guaranteeing that the reactants and catalyst have sufficient contact time [189–192].

Temperature and pressure: Pressure can affect the solubility of reactants and the rate of gas-liquid or liquid-solid interactions whereas higher temperatures typically increase reaction rates by supplying the required activation energy for the reaction. In a continuous flow system, precise control of these parameters enables fine-tuning of reaction kinetics [189, 191, 193].

Catalyst Properties: The catalyst's characteristics such as surface area, particle size, and distribution of active sites are important in establishing the reaction rate. Deactivation and leaching of the catalyst can also affect the kinetics in continuous flow systems. To sustain high reaction rates and selectivity, the catalyst must remain stable and active throughout the reaction [141, 149, 169, 194].

Mass and Heat Transfer: In continuous flow systems it is essential to prevent concentration and temperature gradients that may impact reaction rates and selectivity [189, 193, 195]. The utilization of microreactors, which have high ratios of surface area to volume, improves the transfer of heat and mass, resulting in much more consistent reaction conditions and enhanced kinetic efficiency [39, 41, 46, 120].

In conclusion, different analytical techniques are used in kinetic studies in continuous flow mode to quantify reaction rates and identify the factors affecting the kinetics of NAC reduction. Key factors influencing the reaction kinetics are catalyst properties temperature pressure reactor design and flow rates. By understanding and optimizing these variables, catalytic

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processes for NAC reduction can be made more scalable and efficient [189–195].

7. Challenges and limitations

Even though continuous flow processes have many benefits for reducing NACs, there are a few issues and restrictions that must be resolved to fully utilize their potential. These difficulties include problems with operations and technology as well as financial safety and environmental concerns.

Technical and Operational Challenges.

Catalyst Deactivation: In continuous flow processes, this is one of the main technical difficulties. Because of the leaching of active components, sintering, fouling, or poisoning, catalysts may eventually lose their activity [71, 149, 194]. For instance, the adsorption of reaction intermediates or the formation of carbonaceous deposits can block active sites in catalysts used to reduce NACs such as palladium thereby decreasing the catalyst's efficiency. It is necessary to regularly regenerate or replace the catalyst which can halt the continuous process and raise operating expenses [194–196].

Reactor Design Issues: Another major challenge is designing the ideal reactor for continuous flow processes. Maintaining consistent reaction conditions within the reactor requires ensuring even distribution of the flow, efficient transfer of heat, and avoidance of dead zones or channeling [47, 128, 197]. Although microreactors provide superior control over reaction parameters, they are susceptible to clogging, particularly in the case of heterogeneous catalysts or reactions resulting in solid by-products. Furthermore, careful thought must be given to maintaining the advantages of continuous flow while maintaining efficiency and safety when scaling up from laboratory-scale microreactors to industrial-scale reactors [39, 41, 46, 120, 121].

Economic Considerations.

Setup and maintenance costs: The initial outlay required to set up continuous flow systems can be high. To guarantee exact control of reaction conditions, specialized equipment such as

automated control systems, high-precision pumps, and microreactors is needed. Furthermore, these systems may require expensive maintenance especially if catalyst deactivation occurs frequently and replacement or regeneration is necessary. An additional factor raising the total cost is the requirement for premium materials and components to withstand continuous use [29, 41, 46, 78, 96, 97, 108, 117].

Problems with Scalability: Although continuous flow processes are naturally scalable, there are some obstacles to overcome when moving from laboratory to industrial-scale manufacturing. It can be challenging to guarantee that the process is scaled up while maintaining the same degree of efficiency and control. As the scale grows, elements like heat management, flow distribution, and reactor design get more complicated. Furthermore, it is important to carefully consider whether scaling up is cost-effective because if the costs are too high compared to the volume of production, the advantages of continuous flow may be lost [47, 92, 198, 199].

Safety and environmental concerns.

Environmental Impact: Compared to batch processes, continuous flow processes typically generate less waste and use less energy, but they still have environmental drawbacks. To minimize the impact on the environment, caution must be taken when disposing of catalysts, using solvents, and releasing potentially hazardous intermediates or by-products. While they may necessitate further funding and operational modifications, sustainable techniques like recycling catalysts and solvents and applying green chemistry concepts can help allay these worries [29, 130, 191, 200, 201].

Security Issues: Pressurized operations and the frequent use of dangerous chemicals make continuous flow systems unsafe. It takes powerful design and safety controls to ensure that these systems operate safely and do not leak, blow up, or cause other mishaps. Though it increases setup complexity and expense, the use of automated systems to monitor and control reaction parameters can improve safety. To keep a workplace safe, emergency shutdown procedures and routine safety audits are crucial [202–204].

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The reduction of NACs through continuous flow processes presents several benefits in terms of sustainability, efficiency, and yield. However, some issues need to be resolved. The effective implementation and functioning of these systems depend heavily on many factors including technical ones like reactor design and catalyst deactivation, economic ones like setup and maintenance costs and scalability, and environmental and safety issues. To fully realize the benefits of continuous flow technologies, these issues must be resolved through increased research and development, better catalyst design, and optimized reactor configurations.

8. Future Trends and Developments

The reduction of NACs through continuous flow processes is expected to witness notable progress due to various factors such as novel reactor designs, newly developed catalytic materials, technology integration, and increasing opportunities for industrial application. It is anticipated that these advancements will improve continuous flow systems' scalability, sustainability, and efficiency by increasing their appeal for a variety of applications [34, 81, 82, 112, 131, 132, 156, 159, 160, 167, 176, 205, 206].

Innovations in Flow Reactor Design

At the forefront of developments in flow reactor design are developments in microfluidics and materials science. A growing number of microfluidic reactors are being optimized for the reduction of NACs due to their high surface area-to-volume ratios and precise control over reaction parameters [41, 46, 47, 207]. Complex microreactor geometries that improve heat transfer and mixing efficiency have been made possible by recent advancements in additive manufacturing and 3D printing. Furthermore, the longevity and functionality of microreactors are being enhanced using cutting-edge materials like silicon carbide which provide exceptional thermal conductivity and chemical resistance. It can be anticipated that these advancements will increase the efficiency and versatility of continuous-flow reactors enabling their use in both industrial and laboratory contexts [123, 125, 126, 133, 208, 209].

Novel Catalytic Substances.

A major field of study focused on improving the economic and environmental sustainability of continuous flow processes is the creation of green and sustainable catalysts. Bimetallic nanoparticles, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), and enzyme-mimicking catalysts are a few examples of novel catalytic materials that are being investigated for their potential to achieve high activity and selectivity with minimal environmental impact. When it comes to reducing NACs, for instance, bimetallic catalysts such as Pd-Au, Pt/NiFe, or Ni-Au alloys have demonstrated encouraging outcomes providing enhanced stability and decreased leaching in contrast to conventional single-metal catalysts [165–167, 174, 210–212]. Catalysts are becoming more sustainable due to the addition of biodegradable and renewable supports like chitosan or cellulose [158, 190, 213, 214]. It can be expected that these developments in catalytic materials will greatly increase the sustainability and efficiency of continuous flow systems for NAC reduction.

Combination with Different Technologies.

Continuous flow reactors are becoming more and more integrated with other technologies like photocatalysis and biocatalysis to create hybrid systems that can increase reaction efficiency and expand the range of possible uses [1, 115, 117–119, 191]. Flow reactors and biocatalysis for example can be used together to enhance the benefits of chemical catalysts by utilizing enzymes to carry out highly specific transformations in mild conditions. This hybrid method can be especially helpful in complex reductions where mild reaction conditions and chemo-selectivity are essential. Similarly, photocatalysis can be integrated with flow systems to drive reactions using light, potentially eliminating the need for harsh chemicals and conditions [215–219]. The reduction of NACs and other chemical transformations could be made easier and more sustainably with the help of these hybrid systems.

Opportunities for Commercial Adoption.

Market trends and potential applications in a variety of sectors are driving the increasingly promising prospects for the industrial

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adoption of continuous flow processes for NAC reduction ^[220]. The capacity of continuous flow technologies to yield high-purity products with consistent quality and lower waste is attracting the attention of the pharmaceutical industry ^[221]. To improve sustainability and production efficiency, the agrochemical and fine chemical industries are also investigating continuous flow systems ^[222]. Consistent with the advantages of continuous flow technologies, market trends point to a move toward more economical and environmentally friendly manufacturing methods ^[221]. Furthermore, improvements in catalytic materials and reactor design should reduce entry barriers and increase the accessibility of these systems for a larger spectrum of industries. Businesses will probably adopt continuous flow processes for NAC reduction at a faster rate as they look to reduce their environmental impact and increase operational efficiency ^[223].

9. Summary and Outlook

This review discusses a novel way to address the serious environmental problems caused by NAC contamination: the continuous flow hydrogenation of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) to aromatic amines. With the heavy reliance of sectors like polymers, dyes, and pharmaceuticals on aromatic amines, the ability to recover these valuable products from waste streams represents a significant advancement in sustainable chemical manufacturing. Through optimized catalyst utilization and real-time reaction control, continuous flow processes, as opposed to batch methods, offer improved efficiency, scalability, and safety, while significantly reducing environmental footprints.

Specific control over reaction parameters has been made possible by the development of specialized reactors such as microreactors, packed-bed reactors, membrane reactors, and photocatalytic flow reactors. This has improved product yield and selectivity while guaranteeing the safe handling of hazardous materials. These reactors have many benefits, such as enhanced heat and mass transfer, decreased waste, and shorter operating downtime, especially when combined with cutting-edge catalytic materials. The recovery and reuse of spent catalysts, which is crucial for the long-term sustainability of these processes, is also made possible by the adaptability of continuous flow systems.

Even with these improvements, problems still exist. The long-term stability of processes is still impacted by catalyst deactivation, fouling, and leaching. Additionally, there are technical challenges in maintaining consistent reaction conditions when flow-mode systems are scaled up from laboratory to industrial levels. However, new advancements in green catalysts, bimetallic catalysts, and nanocatalysts, supported by metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and polymer frameworks, promise to overcome these challenges by providing higher stability, selectivity, and recyclability. Reactor design advancements, especially the combination of additive manufacturing and 3D printing, enable the creation of specialized reactor geometries that improve reaction efficiency and mixing on a commercial scope.

Going ahead, continuous flow processes have the potential to completely transform several industries outside chemical production. Industries are facing pressure to adopt more environmentally friendly technologies that minimize waste and reduce resource consumption due to growing environmental regulations and the global shift toward sustainability. Continuous flow technologies can convert hazardous NAC waste into valuable byproducts. This is in line with the principles of the circular economy and offers industries a means of making money from waste recovery in addition to providing an environmental solution.

To boost the adoption of zero-carbon technologies and further reduce energy consumption, future research should concentrate on the integration of continuous flow reactors with renewable energy sources such as solar-driven photocatalytic systems. Further extending the use of these processes in fine chemical synthesis and environmental cleanup, hybrid systems combining flow-mode reactors with biocatalysis or photocatalysis may open new avenues for the selective reduction of complex molecules.

To sum up, the implementation of continuous flow hydrogenation technologies is a significant advancement in environmentally friendly chemistry and bioremediation. Continuous flow systems are poised to be a key component of industrial chemistry's future because they offer an effective,

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scalable, and environmentally friendly substitute for batch processing. Continuous flow processes for NAC reduction are expected to become a key component of sustainable chemical manufacturing, fostering both industrial innovation and environmental preservation as the demand for resource-efficient technologies and cleaner production methods grows globally.

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11. Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in RepOD at <https://doi.org/10.18150/DS8936>, reference number DS8936

12. Declaration statement

The authors declare no competing interests.

13. Credit author contributions

P.N.: Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review and Editing, Visualization; **P.C.:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Methodology, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review and Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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This paper reviews the continuous-flow reduction of nitroaromatic compounds (NACs) into valuable aromatic amines, addressing environmental and industrial challenges. Key topics include reactor designs such as microreactors and packed-bed systems, advanced catalysts like bimetallic nanoparticles, and emerging trends like hybrid photocatalysis. The work emphasizes transforming toxic NAC waste into fine chemical products, aligning with circular economy principles.